

Pseudo-concave Oka domains in projective manifolds

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Abstract

A complex manifold is called an Oka manifold if, for any approximation and interpolation problem of a holomorphic map from an arbitrary Stein manifold, it possesses a continuous solution, that can be deformed to a holomorphic solution via homotopy. In this paper, we focus on the relationship between Oka and pseudo-concavity in domains with boundaries, and generalizes the theorem about pseudo-concave Oka domains in projective spaces, originally proven by Forstnerič [7], to the case of projective manifolds. Finally, we show that a complex surface without compactification constructed by Honda-Nakata [12] possesses a certain type of Oka property.

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1 Introduction

The concept of Oka manifold has its origin in the *Oka's principle* discovered in Kiyoshi Oka's Paper III [17]. The Oka's principle means the *phenomenon that the solvability of a complex analytic problem on a Stein manifold is determined by a topological condition*.

It is generally difficult to determine whether a complex manifold is Oka from its definition, and many examples of Oka manifolds have been discovered by examining the sufficient condition called *Gromov ellipticity* [11]. It is one of the anti-hyperbolic characteristics.

On the other hand, in recent years, there has been discussion about the *dual Levi problem*, which attempts to find out the characteristics of Oka manifolds from their boundary conditions, and in particular the relationship between Levi pseudo-concavity and Oka. Although no clear argument for the dual Levi problem has been obtained at present, Kusakabe has proposed that , in Stein manifolds of two or more dimensions (especially \mathbb{C}^n ($n > 1$)), a domain obtained by removing some compact convex set is an Oka manifold [16] . Furthermore, Forstnerič has shown that the analogous argument holds for the complex projective space \mathbb{P}^n ($n > 1$) [7, Theorem 5.1] . In the proof of these results, the so called *density property* and Theorem 1.3 [16, Theorem 1.2] plays a fundamental role.

Definition 1.1 (Varolin [19]). A complex manifold X has the *density property* if every holomorphic vector field on X can be approximated uniformly on compacts by Lie combinations (sums and commutators) of complete holomorphic vector fields on X .

Remark 1.2. There are the following facts:

- (i) Any Stein manifold with the density property is of dimension at least two and is Oka (cf. [6, Theorem 5.5.18]).
- (ii) \mathbb{C}^n ($n > 1$) has the density property (cf. [9, Example 2.7]).

By using the Andersén-Lempert theorem which is one of the Multivariable Complex Dynamical Methods, the following statement has been shown:

Theorem 1.3 (Kusakabe [16, Theorem 1.2]). *Let Y be a Stein manifold with the density property. Then, for any compact $\mathcal{O}(Y)$ -convex subset $K \subset Y$, $Y \setminus K$ is Oka.*

We present two main results of this paper. One of the results is Theorem 1.4 which generalizes the theorem about pseudo-concave Oka domains in projective spaces given in Forstnerič [7, Theorem 5.1] to general projective manifolds.

Theorem 1.4 (Theorem 3.5). *Let $L \rightarrow X$ be a positive line bundle over a projective manifold X and $V \in |L|$ be a divisor s.t. $\Omega := X \setminus V$ has the density property. Then, for any compact $\mathcal{O}(\Omega)$ -convex subset $K \subset \Omega$, $X \setminus K$ is Oka.*

This theorem is proven by considering the projective space in which the projective manifold X is embedded, and then pulling the argument in Forstnerič [7, Theorem 5.1] back to X . As a Corollary from Theorem 1.4, the following holds:

Corollary 1.5 (Corollary 3.17). *For any point $y \in Y$ in a rationally homogeneous manifold Y of dimension at least two, if we take a sufficiently small closed ball B centered at y , then, $Y \setminus B$ is Oka.*

The motivation for expecting Theorem 1.4 to hold was the assumption that *the complex surface without compactification* constructed in Honda-Nakata [12] would enjoy some kind of Oka properties. *Not admitting a compactification* here means that there is no compact complex surface that includes it as an open subset. Such a complex surface can be constructed from $\mathbb{P}^1 \times \mathbb{P}^1 \setminus K$, where $K \subset \mathbb{P}^1 \times \mathbb{P}^1$ is a compact holomorphically convex subset. We can show such a domain is an Oka domain by Theorem 1.4. By using the method used in the proof of Theorem 1.4, we can construct such a complex surface without compactification, which has the *Oka-1 property*, a weaker condition than Oka property (Definition 4.1, Theorem 4.19). Theorem 4.19 is the second main result in this paper.

Moreover, it can be easily confirmed that such a complex surface has rationally connectedness, which states that any two points on it are connected by a finite chain of rational curves (Proposition 4.13). In fact, the complex surface constructed in Honda-Nakata [12] is a *minitwistor space* which has rational curves (*minitwistor lines*) whose self-intersection number is two, and the space of these curves forms the three-dimensional complex manifold. Such a anti-hyperbolicity is also one of the motivations for the complex surface constructed by Honda-Nakata [12] to have some kind of Okaness.

In Section 2, we recall the relationship between Oka manifolds and holomorphic flexibilities, and the dual Levi problem. In Section 3, we prove Theorem 1.4. In Section 4, as an application of the method used in Theorem 1.4, we construct the rationally connected Oka-1 surface without compactification.

2 Oka manifolds and the dual Levi problem

2.1 Oka manifolds and holomorphic flexibilities

In this paper, a complex manifold is assumed to be connected and satisfy the second countability axiom.

In this section, we recall the definition of Oka manifolds and the properties called *holomorphic flexibility* (cf. [5]). First, we recall some notations and statements about in complex analysis.

Definition 2.1. Let $K \subset X$ be a compact subset in a complex manifold X . The holomorphically convex hull $\widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(X)}$ of K in X (or $\mathcal{O}(X)$ -convex hull of K) is defined as follows:

$$\widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(X)} := \left\{ p \in X : |f(p)| \leq \max_{x \in K} |f(x)|, \forall f \in \mathcal{O}(X) \right\}$$

Moreover,

K is compact holomorphically convex in X (or is compact $\mathcal{O}(X)$ -convex) $\stackrel{\text{def}}{\iff} \widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(X)} = K$.

Hereafter, when we speak of a *holomorphic function f on a compact subset $K \subset X$ in a complex manifold X* ($f \in \mathcal{O}(X)$), we think f is defined on some open neighborhood of K in X .

On Stein manifolds, the following approximation theorem holds:

Theorem 2.2 (Oka Weil approximation theorem [6, Theorem 2.8.4]). *Let X be a Stein manifold. For any compact $\mathcal{O}(X)$ -convex subset $K \subset X$ and holomorphic function $f \in \mathcal{O}(K)$, f can be uniformly approximated on K by holomorphic maps $\tilde{f} \in \mathcal{O}(X)$ (i.e. If we take a hermitian metric h on X , $\forall \varepsilon > 0$, $\exists \tilde{f} \in \mathcal{O}(X)$ s.t. $\text{dist}_h(f(x), \tilde{f}(x)) < \varepsilon$, $\forall x \in K$).*

As we will see next, Oka manifold is defined as the dual concept of Stein manifold.

Definition 2.3 ([6, Definition 5.4.1]). A complex manifold Y is an Oka manifold if, for any holomorphic map $f : K \rightarrow Y$ defined on a neighborhood of any compact convex set $K \subset \mathbb{C}^n$ ($n \in \mathbb{N}$), f can be approximated uniformly on K by holomorphic maps $F : \mathbb{C}^n \rightarrow Y$. In this case, Y is said to enjoy CAP (Convex Approximation Property).

When the Oka manifold is defined in this way, the following Oka principle holds:

Theorem 2.4 (Forstnerič's Oka principle [6, Corollary 5.4.5]). *Suppose that the complex manifold Y satisfies CAP. Then, for any Stein manifold X , compact $\mathcal{O}(X)$ -convex set $K \subset X$, closed complex submanifold $X' \subset X$, and continuous map $f_0 : X \rightarrow Y$ which is holomorphic on a neighborhood of K and X' , there exists a homotopy $f_t : X \rightarrow Y$ ($t \in [0, 1]$) that satisfies the following condition for all $t \in [0, 1]$:*

(i) $f_t|_{X'} = f_0|_{X'}$ (Interpolation).

(ii) f_t is holomorphic on K and approximates f_0 uniformly on K (Approximation).

(iii) $f_1 : X \rightarrow Y$ is holomorphic.

Furthermore, if f_0 is holomorphic on a open neighborhood of X' , then f_t can be taken to be tangent to f_0 along X' with a given finite order (Jet Interpolation).

By the Forstnerič's Oka principle, the following statement immediately holds:

Theorem 2.5 ([6, Theorem 5.6.5]). *Let $E \rightarrow B$ be holomorphic fiber bundle with the Oka fiber. Then,*

$$E : Oka \iff B : Oka$$

By the above theorem and the uniformization theorem on Riemann surfaces, the following statement also holds:

Corollary 2.6 ([6, Corollary 5.6.4]). *For any Riemann surface Y , the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (i) $Y : Oka$.
- (ii) $Y : \text{not Kobayashi hyperbolic}$.
- (iii) $Y : \mathbb{P}^1, \mathbb{C}, \mathbb{C}^*$ or \mathbb{T} .

It is generally difficult to directly determine whether a complex manifold is Oka or not from such definitions. Therefore, by introducing certain anti-hyperbolic properties called *holomorphic flexibilities*, we can see the geometric characteristics of Oka manifolds. Simply put, *holomorphic flexibility* means that there are many non-degenerate holomorphic maps from the complex Euclidean space.

Definition 2.7. Let Y be a complex manifold.

$Y : \mathbb{C} - \text{connected} \stackrel{\text{def}}{\iff} \forall x, y \in Y, \exists \text{ a finite number of holomorphic maps } f_j : \mathbb{C} \rightarrow Y, (j = 1, \dots, m) \text{ s.t. } x \in f_1(\mathbb{C}), y \in f_m(\mathbb{C}), f_j(\mathbb{C}) \cap f_{j+1}(\mathbb{C}) \neq \emptyset, (j = 1, \dots, m-1)$.

Definition 2.8 ([6, Definition 7.1.7]). Let Y be a complex manifold.

- (i) $Y : \text{dominable} \stackrel{\text{def}}{\iff} \exists y \in Y, \exists f \in \mathcal{O}(\mathbb{C}^n, Y) \text{ s.t. } f(0) = y, df_0(\mathbb{C}^n) = T_y Y$.
- (ii) $Y : \text{strongly dominable} \stackrel{\text{def}}{\iff} Y \text{ is dominable at } \forall y \in Y$.

Definition 2.9 (cf. [6, Definition 5.6.13]). Let Y be a complex manifold.

- (i) $Y : \text{subelliptic} \stackrel{\text{def}}{\iff} \exists \text{ a finite number of holomorphic vector bundles } E_j \rightarrow Y, \exists \text{ holomorphic maps } s_j : E_j \rightarrow Y (j = 1, \dots, m) \text{ s.t. } \forall y \in Y,$
 - (a) $s_j(0_y) = y, 0_y \in E_{j,y} : \text{origin } (j = 1, \dots, m),$
 - (b) $(ds_1)_{0_y}(E_{1,y}) + \dots + (ds_m)_{0_y}(E_{m,y}) = T_y Y$.
- (ii) $Y : \text{elliptic} \stackrel{\text{def}}{\iff} Y \text{ is subelliptic in the case of } j = 1$.

elliptic \implies *Oka* has been proved by Gromov [11] and *subelliptic* \implies *Oka* has been proved by Forstnerič (cf. [6, Corollary 5.6.14]). Thus, we can easily check the following relation:

$$\text{elliptic} \implies \text{subelliptic} \implies \text{Oka} \implies \text{strongly dominable} \implies \mathbb{C}\text{-connected}.$$

2.2 The dual Levi problem

The Levi problem is the question of what boundary conditions are satisfied for a domain with C^2 -boundary in a complex manifold when that domain is Stein. Before seeing the result of the Levi problem, we recall the *Levi pseudo-convexity*:

Definition 2.10 ([6, Definition 2.1.1]). Let $\Omega \subset X$ be a domain with C^2 -boundary in a complex manifold X , i.e. $\exists U$: an open neighborhood of $\partial\Omega$ and $\exists \rho : U \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$: a real valued C^2 -function s.t.

$$\Omega \cap U = \{x \in U \mid \rho(x) < 0\}, \quad d\rho_x \neq 0 \quad (\forall x \in \partial\Omega).$$

Then, for such a domain, we define the Levi pseudo convexity as follows:

$$(2.1) \quad \Omega : \text{Levi pseudo-convex} \stackrel{\text{def}}{\iff} \sqrt{-1}\partial\bar{\partial}\rho \geq 0 \quad \text{on } \ker \partial\rho \cap TX|_{\partial\Omega}$$

Remark 2.11. Let $\Omega \subset X$ be a domain with C^2 -boundary in a complex manifold X .

$$(i) \quad \Omega : \text{Levi pseudo-concave} \stackrel{\text{def}}{\iff} \sqrt{-1}\partial\bar{\partial}\rho \leq 0 \quad \text{on } \ker \partial\rho \cap TX|_{\partial\Omega}$$

(ii) If $\Omega \subset X$ is Levi pseudo-convex, then $X \setminus \bar{\Omega} \subset X$ is Levi pseudo-concave.

The Levi problem has been solved on Stein manifolds as the following statement:

Theorem 2.12 (Docquier-Grauert [2]). *Let $\Omega \subset X$ be a domain with C^2 -boundary in a Stein manifold X . Then,*

$$\Omega : \text{Stein} \iff \Omega : \text{Levi pseudo-convex}$$

If we take X as a general complex manifold, Theorem 2.12 doesn't hold. In fact, let $\pi : Bl_0(\mathbb{C}^2) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^2$ be the blow-up of \mathbb{C}^2 at the origin. Then, $\pi^{-1}(\mathbb{B}^2) \subset Bl_0(\mathbb{C}^2)$ is Levi pseudo-convex but not Stein.

As the dual problem to the Levi problem, the *dual Levi problem* has been given as follows:

Problem 2.13 (The dual Levi problem). Let $\Omega \subset X$ be a domain with C^2 -boundary in a complex manifold X . What are the geometric necessary conditions, sufficient conditions, and necessary and sufficient conditions for the boundary $\partial\Omega$ when Ω is to Oka?

There are some consequences from which we could expect a relationship between Oka and pseudo convexity;

Theorem 2.14 (Kusakabe, [16, Theorem 1.2] [14, Lemma 3.3]). *Let Y be a Stein manifold with the density property.*

(i) $\forall K \subset Y$: compact $\mathcal{O}(Y)$ -convex subset, $Y \setminus K$ is an Oka domain.

(ii) In particular, if Y is of dimension at least three [7, Theorem 5.1] and K has an infinite derived set, then $Y \setminus K$ is not subelliptic.

Corollary 2.15 (Kusakabe, [16, Corollary 1.3]). $\forall K \subset \mathbb{C}^n$ ($n > 1$) : compact convex subset, $\mathbb{C}^n \setminus K$ is Oka.

Corollary 2.16. $\mathbb{C}^n \setminus \bar{\mathbb{B}}^n$ ($n > 2$) is non-subelliptic Oka.

3 Pseudo-concave Oka domains in projective manifolds

In this section, we generalize the theorem about pseudo-concave Oka domains in projective spaces, which has been proven in Forstnerič [7, Theorem 5.1], to general projective manifolds. The proof is based on the idea used in Forstnerič [7, Theorem 5.1].

First, the original Forstnerič's statement is as follows:

Theorem 3.1 ([7, Theorem 5.1]). *Let $\Lambda \subset \mathbb{P}^n$ ($n > 1$) be a hypersurface s.t. $\Omega = \mathbb{P}^n \setminus \Lambda$ has the density property (Definition 1.1). Then, for any compact $\mathcal{O}(\Omega)$ -convex subset $K \subset \Omega$, $\mathbb{P}^n \setminus K$ is Oka.*

One of the reasons why the stage considered in the above theorem is complex projective spaces \mathbb{P}^n is that the following theorem holds on \mathbb{P}^n .

Theorem 3.2 ([7, Cor A.5]). *Let $\{V_t\}_{t \in [0,1]} \subset \mathcal{V}_k(\mathbb{P}^n)$ be a path of hyper surfaces of degree k in \mathbb{P}^n and $K \subset \mathbb{P}^n$ be a compact subset s.t. $K \cap V_t = \emptyset$ ($\forall t \in [0, 1]$) and K is compact $\mathcal{O}(\mathbb{P}^n \setminus V_1)$ -convex. Then, $\forall t \in [0, 1]$, K is compact $\mathcal{O}(\mathbb{P}^n \setminus V_t)$ -convex.*

In the above theorem, the path of hypersurfaces in \mathbb{P}^n , or more generally the path of hypersurfaces in the product $\mathbb{P}^n \times \mathbb{P}^m$ of complex projective spaces, has the following meaning (cf. [7, APPENDIX A]):

First, we introduce the following symbols;

- $\mathcal{V}_k(\mathbb{P}^n)$: the space of hypersurfaces of degree k in \mathbb{P}^n .
- $\mathcal{V}_{k,l}(\mathbb{P}^n \times \mathbb{P}^m)$: the space of hypersurfaces of degree (k, l) in $\mathbb{P}^n \times \mathbb{P}^m$.
- $\mathcal{H}(k, n)$: the space of homogeneous complex polynomials of degree k in $n + 1$ variables.
- $\mathcal{H}(k, n; l, m)$: the space of homogeneous complex polynomials of degree (k, l) in $n+1$ variables and $m + 1$ variables.

Putting $N = \binom{n+k}{k} \binom{m+l}{l} - 1$, we have the following natural projection:

$$\mathbb{C}^{N+1} \setminus \{0\} \simeq \mathcal{H}(k, n; l, m) \longrightarrow \mathcal{V}_{k,l}(\mathbb{P}^n \times \mathbb{P}^m) \simeq \mathbb{P}^N, P \mapsto V(P)$$

Where $V(P) := \{(z, w) \in \mathbb{P}^n \times \mathbb{P}^m ; P(z, w) = 0\}$ for $P \in \mathcal{H}(k, n; l, m)$.

Since the above projection is a holomorphic \mathbb{C}^* -bundle over \mathbb{P}^N , any path in $\mathbb{P}^N \simeq \mathcal{V}_{k,l}(\mathbb{P}^n \times \mathbb{P}^m)$ can be lifted to a path in $\mathbb{C}^{N+1} \setminus \{0\} \simeq \mathcal{H}(k, n; l, m)$. i.e. any path in $\mathcal{V}_{k,l}(\mathbb{P}^n \times \mathbb{P}^m)$ is given by a path $\{P_t\}_{t \in [0,1]} \subset \mathcal{H}(k, n; l, m)$ as the form $\{V(P_t)\}_{t \in [0,1]} \subset \mathcal{V}_{k,l}(\mathbb{P}^n \times \mathbb{P}^m)$.

The essence of Theorem 3.2 is the *Chow's theorem*, any hypersurface (more generally, any analytic subset) on \mathbb{P}^n can be expressed as zeros of homogeneous polynomials with homogeneous coordinates of \mathbb{P}^n . Focusing on this, we can show that Theorem 3.2 can be generalized as follows:

Theorem 3.3. *Let $L \rightarrow X$ be a positive line bundle over a projective manifold. Furthermore, Let $\{V_t\}_{t \in [0,1]} \subset |L|$ be a path in the complete linear system $|L|$, $K \subset X$ be a compact subset s.t. $K \cap V_t = \emptyset$ ($\forall t \in [0, 1]$) and K is compact $\mathcal{O}(X \setminus V_1)$ -convex. Then, $\forall t \in [0, 1]$, K is compact $\mathcal{O}(X \setminus V_t)$ -convex.*

In the above theorem, a path in the complete linear system $|L|$ has the following meaning: The complete linear system $|L|$ is the set of all the divisors $\text{div}(s)$ that are determined from the zeros of the holomorphic sections $s \in H^0(X, \mathcal{O}(L)) \setminus \{0\}$. Then, there exists the following bijection as a set (cf. [9, Proposition 3.7(i)]):

$$|L| \longleftrightarrow \mathbb{P}(H^0(X, \mathcal{O}(L)) \simeq \mathbb{P}^{N^*}), \quad s \mapsto \text{div}(s), \quad (N = \dim(H^0(X, \mathcal{O}(L))).$$

\mathbb{P}^{N^*} is the space obtained by parameterizing all the hyperplanes in \mathbb{P}^N (cf. [10, p.177]). By the above bijection, we call the subset of $|L|$ corresponding to the path in \mathbb{P}^{N^*} the path in $|L|$. Explicitly, when we take some base s_0, s_1, \dots, s_N of $H^0(X, \mathcal{O}(L))$, a path in $|L|$ is given by some continuous path $r : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^{N+1}$, $r(t) = (x_0(t), x_1(t), \dots, x_N(t))$ as the following form:

$$\{V_t\}_{t \in [0,1]} \subset |L|, \quad V_t = \text{div}(x_0(t)s_0(t), x_1(t)s_1(t), \dots, x_N(t)s_N(t)).$$

Remark 3.4. Let L be a holomorphic line bundle.

- (i) Given a path $\{V_t\}_{t \in [0,1]} \subset |L|$, for any $k > 0$, $\{kV_t\}_{t \in [0,1]}$ is a path in $|L^{\otimes k}|$.
- (ii) If L is very ample, by considering $X \subset \mathbb{P}^N$ by the rational map $\Phi_L : X \rightarrow \mathbb{P}^N$ associated with $|L|$, any path in $|L|$ is given by some path of hypersurfaces $\{\Lambda_t\}_{t \in [0,1]} \subset \mathbb{P}^N$ as the following form : $\{X \cap \Lambda_t\}_{t \in [0,1]} \subset \mathbb{P}^N$.
- (iii) If L is positive, $X \setminus V$ is a Stein domain for any $V \in |L|$. In fact, since L is positive, if we take a sufficiently large positive integer $k \gg 0$, $L^{\otimes k}$ becomes a very ample, and the rational mapping $\Phi_{L^{\otimes k}} : X \rightarrow \mathbb{P}^N$ associated with $|L^{\otimes k}|$ embeds X into \mathbb{P}^N . From the way this rational map is defined, divisor kV is a restriction kV of a certain hyperplane H on \mathbb{P}^N to X . Therefore, $X \setminus V = X \setminus kV \subset \mathbb{P}^N \setminus H \simeq \mathbb{C}^N$.

By using Theorem 3.3, the following theorem holds, which is a generalization of Theorem 3.1 to projective manifolds:

Theorem 3.5 (Theorem 1.4). *Let $L \rightarrow X$ be a positive line bundle over a projective manifold X and $V \in |L|$ be a divisor s.t. $\Omega := X \setminus V$ has the density property. Then, for any compact $\mathcal{O}(\Omega)$ -convex subset $K \subset \Omega$, $X \setminus K$ is Oka.*

From now, we will prove some claims to provide the proof of Theorem 3.5. The following Theorem 3.6 is Forstnerič [7, Theorem A.1] itself:

Theorem 3.6 ([7, Theorem A.1]). *Let $K \subset X$ be a compact subset in a Stein manifold X and $f : [0, 1] \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ be a continuous and X -holomorphic map (i.e. for each $t \in [0, 1]$, $f_t := f(t, *) : X \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ is a holomorphic function) s.t. f has no zeros on $[0, 1] \times K$, $f_1 : X \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ has no zeros on $\widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(X)}$. Then, for any $t \in [0, 1]$, the hypersurface $V_t := \{x \in X; f_t(x) = 0\}$ doesn't intersect with $\widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(X)}$.*

In the proof of Theorem 3.6, the following Lemma 3.7 is used.

Lemma 3.7. *For any holomorphic function g defined on $\widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(X)}$, the following condition holds:*

$$(3.1) \quad \sup_K |g| = \sup_{\widehat{K}} |g|$$

Proof. Since $K \subset \widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(X)}$, $\sup_K |g| \leq \sup_{\widehat{K}} |g|$ is obvious. Therefore, we only need to show the inverse inequality. Since K is compact subset on the Stein manifold X , \widehat{K} is compact. By the Oka-Weil approximation theorem, $\forall \epsilon > 0$, $\exists g_\epsilon \in \mathcal{O}(X)$ s.t.

$$(3.2) \quad \sup_{x \in \widehat{K}} |g(x) - g_\epsilon(x)| < \epsilon$$

Next, by the definition of \widehat{K} , $|g_\epsilon(x)| \leq \sup_K |g_\epsilon|$ ($\forall x \in \widehat{K}$), and hence

$$(3.3) \quad \sup_{\widehat{K}} |g_\epsilon| \leq \sup_K |g_\epsilon|.$$

$\forall x \in \widehat{K}$, by (3.2) and (3.3),

$$(3.4) \quad |g(x)| \leq |g_\epsilon(x)| + |g(x) - g_\epsilon(x)| \leq \sup_{\widehat{K}} |g_\epsilon| + \epsilon \leq \sup_K |g_\epsilon| + \epsilon.$$

Since (3.4) holds for any $x \in \widehat{K}$,

$$(3.5) \quad \sup_{\widehat{K}} |g| \leq \sup_K |g_\epsilon| + \epsilon.$$

On the other hand, by (3.2),

$$(3.6) \quad \sup_K |g_\epsilon| \leq \sup_{y \in K} (|g(y)| + |g_\epsilon(y) - g(y)|) \leq \sup_K |g| + \sup_{\widehat{K}} |g_\epsilon - g| \leq \sup_K |g| + \epsilon.$$

From the above, by (3.5) and (3.6),

$$\sup_{\widehat{K}} |g| \leq \sup_K |g| + 2\epsilon.$$

Since we can take $\epsilon > 0$ arbitrarily, $\sup_{\widehat{K}} |g| \leq \sup_K |g|$. □

Next, we give the proof of Theorem 3.6.

Proof of Theorem 3.6 ([7, Theorem A.1]). Assume that there exists some $t \in [0, 1]$ s.t. the hypersurface $V_t := \{x \in X; f_t(x) = 0\}$ intersects with \widehat{K} . i.e. Putting

$$A := \left\{ t \in [0, 1]; V_t \cap \widehat{K} \neq \emptyset \right\} \subset [0, 1],$$

we assume $A \neq \emptyset$. Since A is compact, we can take $t_0 := \max_A \{t\}$. Let's take a sequence $\{t_n\} \subset (t_0, 1]$ which decreases monotonically toward t_0 . Since f_{t_n} has no zeros on \widehat{K} , $1/f_{t_n} \in \mathcal{O}(\widehat{K})$. Although $\sup_{\widehat{K}} |1/f_{t_n}|$ diverge to infinity when $t_n \searrow t_0$, by Lemma 3.7, $\forall t \in [0, 1]$, $\sup_{\widehat{K}} |1/f_t| = \sup_K |1/f_t| \leq \sup_{[0,1] \times K} |1/f| < \infty$. This is a contradiction. □

From Theorem 3.6, the following Corollary immediately follows:

Corollary 3.8 ([7, Corollary A.2]). *Let $K \subset X$ be a compact subset on a Stein manifold X . Furthermore, Let $V_t = \{f_t = 0\} \subset X$, ($t \in [0, 1]$) be a path of hypersurfaces determined by a continuous and X -holomorphic function $f : [0, 1] \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$. If $\{V_t\}_{t \in [0,1]} \subset X$ satisfies the following conditions:*

(i) $K \cap V_t = \emptyset, \forall t \in [0, 1]$,

(ii) For all compact subset $L \subset X$, there exists some $t_0 \in [0, 1)$ s.t. $\forall t \in [t_0, 1)$, $L \cap V_t = \emptyset$ (i.e. V_t diverge to infinity in X as $t \nearrow 1$).

Then, $\widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(X)} \cap V_t = \emptyset, \forall t \in [0, 1)$.

Proof. Since X is Stein, $\widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(X)}$ is compact. Hence, by the condition (i), there is some $t_0 \in [0, 1)$ s.t. for any $t_1 \in [t_0, 1)$, $\widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(X)} \cap V_{t_1} = \emptyset$. Therefore, for any $t \in [0, 1)$, if we take $t_1 \in [t_0, 1)$, then $t \in [0, t_1]$ and $\widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(X)} \cap V_{t_1} = \emptyset$. From this and condition (ii), we can apply Theorem 3.6, then $\widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(X)} \cap V_{t_2} = \emptyset, \forall t_2 \in [0, t_1)$ holds. In particular, Since $\widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(X)} \cap V_t = \emptyset$ and $t \in [0, 1)$ can be taken arbitrarily, the statement is shown. \square

From Corollary 3.8, the following Corollary 3.9 and 3.10 holds:

Corollary 3.9. Let $L \rightarrow X$ be a positive line bundle over a projective manifold X . Furthermore, let $\{V_t\}_{t \in [0, 1]} \subset |L|$ be a path in $|L|$ and $K \subset X$ be a compact subset s.t. $K \cap V_t = \emptyset (\forall t \in [0, 1])$. If we set $Y := X \setminus V_1$, then $\forall t \in [0, 1]$, $\widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(Y)} \cap V_t = \emptyset$.

Proof. By taking a sufficiently large positive integer $k \gg 0$, $L^{\otimes k}$ becomes very ample. Let $\Phi := \Phi_{L^{\otimes k}} : X \rightarrow \mathbb{P}^N$ be the rational map associated with $|L^{\otimes k}|$. Since, $\{kV_t\}_{t \in [0, 1]}$ is a path in $|L^{\otimes k}|$, there is a path of hyperplanes $\{\Lambda_t\}_{t \in [0, 1]} \subset \mathbb{P}^N$, i.e. there is a path $\{P_t\} \subset \mathcal{H}(1, N)$ which express $\{kV_t\}_{t \in [0, 1]}$ as follows:

$$kV_t = \Phi^*(\Lambda_t) = \{P_t \circ \Phi = 0\} \subset X$$

- The case of $t = 1$.

From how to define Y , $\widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(Y)} \cap V_1 \subset Y \cap V_1 = \emptyset$.

- The case of $t \in (0, 1]$.

Setting $f_t := (P_t \circ \Phi)/(P_1 \circ \Phi) = (P_t/P_1) \circ \Phi$, by the assumption, $f_t \in \mathcal{O}(Y)$. Then, by Remark 3.4, Y is Stein. Moreover, a path $\{f_t = 0\} \subset Y$ of hypersurfaces in Stein manifold Y satisfies the following condition: $\{f_t = 0\}$ diverge to infinity in Y as $t \nearrow 1$.

In fact, let's arbitrarily take a compact subset $K \subset Y$, and fix a point $x \in K$. Since $\lim_{t \rightarrow 1} |f_t(x)| = 1$,

$$0 \leq \exists t_x < 1 \text{ s.t. } t_x \leq \forall t < 1 \implies |f_t(x)| > 1/2.$$

Since K is compact, we can take $t_0 := \max_{x \in K} \{t_x\}$, and then,

$$t_0 \leq \forall t < 1 \implies \{f_t = 0\} \cap K = \emptyset.$$

Therefore, $\{f_t = 0\}$ diverge to infinity as $t \nearrow 1$ in Y .

From Corollary 3.8, $\widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(Y)} \cap \{f_t = 0\} = \emptyset (\forall t \in [0, 1))$, i.e. $\widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(Y)} \cap V_t = \emptyset (\forall t \in [0, 1))$. \square

Corollary 3.10. Let $L \rightarrow X$ be a very ample line bundle over a projective manifold X . We consider X as $X \subset \mathbb{P}^N$ by the rational mapping embedding associated with $|L|$. Let $B \subset \mathcal{V}_1(\mathbb{P}^N) = \mathbb{P}^{N*}$ be a non-empty domain and $\Omega(B) \subset \mathbb{P}^N$ be the union of all hyperplanes $\Lambda \in B$. Then, for any $\Lambda \in B$, $N := X \setminus \Omega(B)$ is compact $\mathcal{O}(X \setminus \Lambda)$ -convex.

Proof. Let's fix one hyperplane $\Lambda \in B$. Then, $\forall z \in \Omega(B) \setminus \Lambda$, there is a hyperplane $\Lambda_0 \in B$ which contains z . Since B is connected, there is a path $\{\Lambda_t\}_{t \in [0,1]} \subset B$ ($\Lambda_1 = \Lambda$) which connects Λ_0 and Λ . Then, by restricting this path to be on X , we obtain a path $\{V_t = X \cap \Lambda_t\} \subset |L|$ in $|L|$. From the way the compact subset $N \subset X \setminus \Lambda = X \setminus V_1$ is defined, $N \cap V_t = \emptyset$ ($\forall t \in [0, 1]$). Hence, by Corollary 3.9,

$$\widehat{N}_{\mathcal{O}(X \setminus V_1)} \cap V_t = \widehat{N}_{\mathcal{O}(X \setminus \Lambda)} \cap \Lambda_t = \emptyset \quad (\forall t \in [0, 1]).$$

In particular, $\widehat{N}_{\mathcal{O}(X \setminus \Lambda)} \cap \Lambda_0 = \emptyset$, $z \notin \widehat{N}_{\mathcal{O}(X \setminus \Lambda)}$ holds. Since $z \in \Omega(B) \setminus \Lambda$ can be taken arbitrarily,

$$\widehat{N}_{\mathcal{O}(X \setminus \Lambda)} \cap (\Omega(B) \setminus \Lambda) = \emptyset.$$

Recall $N = X \setminus \Omega(B)$, i.e.

$$(3.7) \quad X \setminus \widehat{\Omega(B)}_{\mathcal{O}(X \setminus \Lambda)} \cap (\Omega(B) \setminus \Lambda) = \emptyset.$$

(3.7) means that $\widehat{N}_{\mathcal{O}(X \setminus \Lambda)}$ which is the holomorphic convex-hull of $N = X \setminus \Omega(B)$ in $X \setminus \Lambda$ is equal to N . Therefore, $\widehat{N}_{\mathcal{O}(X \setminus \Lambda)} = N$. \square

By using Corollary 3.10 and the following Lemma 3.11, Theorem 3.3 is proven.

Lemma 3.11. *Let X be a complex manifold and $K \subset L \subset X$ be two compact subsets in X . Then, the following statements are hold:*

- (i) $\widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(L)} \subset \widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(X)}$ (and hence, K : compact $\mathcal{O}(X)$ -convex $\implies K$: compact $\mathcal{O}(L)$ -convex).
- (ii) Let X be a Stein manifold.
 K : compact $\mathcal{O}(L)$ -convex, L : compact $\mathcal{O}(X)$ -convex $\implies K$: compact $\mathcal{O}(X)$ -convex.

Proof.

$$\widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(L)} = \left\{ p \in L : |f(p)| \leq \max_{x \in K} |f(x)|, \forall f \in \mathcal{O}(L) \right\}$$

$$\widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(X)} = \left\{ p \in X : |f(p)| \leq \max_{x \in K} |f(x)|, \forall f \in \mathcal{O}(X) \right\}$$

Since the restriction of $f \in \mathcal{O}(X)$ to be on L is $f|_L \in \mathcal{O}(L)$, $\widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(L)} \subset \widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(X)}$. Hence (i) has been proven.

Next, we will show (ii). Since

$$\widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(X)} = \left\{ p \in X : |f(p)| \leq \max_{x \in K} |f(x)|, \forall f \in \mathcal{O}(X) \right\} \subset \widehat{L}_{\mathcal{O}(X)} = L,$$

as elements of $\widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(X)}$, we only need to consider on L . Since K is holomorphically convex in L , $\forall p \in L \setminus K = L \setminus \widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(L)}$, $\exists g \in \mathcal{O}(L)$ s.t. $g(x) > \sup_K |g|$. Furthermore, for the compact holomorphically convex subset $L \subset X$ in Stein manifold X , by using the Oka-Weil approximation theorem, there exist $f \in \mathcal{O}(X)$ which uniformly approximate $g \in \mathcal{O}(L)$ on L and satisfy $f(x) > \sup_K |f|$. Hence, $x \notin L \setminus \widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(X)}$. From the above, $\widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(X)} \subset \widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(L)} = K$ i.e. $\widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(X)} = K$. \square

Proof of Theorem 3.3. Similar to Corollary 3.9, by taking a sufficiently large positive integer $k \gg 0$, $L^{\otimes k}$ becomes very ample and by considering X as $X \subset \mathbb{P}^N$ by the rational mapping embedding $\Phi := \Phi_{L^{\otimes k}} : X \rightarrow \mathbb{P}^N$ associated with $|L^{\otimes k}|$, a path $\{kV_t\}_{t \in [0,1]}$ in $|L^{\otimes k}|$ is expressed by a path of hyperplanes $\{\Lambda_t\}_{t \in [0,1]} \subset \mathbb{P}^N$ as follows: $kV_t = X \cap \Lambda_t$ ($t \in [0,1]$). By the assumption, $(X \cap \Lambda_t) \cap K = \Lambda_t \cap K = \emptyset$ ($t \in [0,1]$), and hence there exists a sufficiently small connected open neighborhood $B \subset \mathbb{P}^{N^*}$ of the path $\{\Lambda_t\}_{t \in [0,1]} \subset \mathbb{P}^{N^*}$ s.t.

$$(3.8) \quad \Omega(B) \cap K = \emptyset$$

where $\Omega(B) \subset \mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^N$ is the union of all hypersurfaces $\Lambda \in B$. By Corollary 3.10, for each $t \in [0,1]$, $N := X \setminus \Omega(B)$ is compact $\mathcal{O}(X \setminus \Lambda_t)$ -convex, i.e. compact $\mathcal{O}(X \setminus V_t)$ -convex. By the assumption, K is compact $\mathcal{O}(X \setminus V_1)$ -convex, and from (3.8), $K \subset N (\subset X \setminus V_1)$, so by Lemma 3.11,

$$(3.9) \quad \widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(N)} \subset \widehat{K}_{\mathcal{O}(X \setminus V_1)} = K$$

Therefore, K is compact $\mathcal{O}(N)$ -convex. For each $t \in [0,1]$, K is compact $\mathcal{O}(X \setminus V_t)$ -convex, and hence for $K \subset N \subset X \setminus V_t$, by using Lemma 3.11, K is compact $\mathcal{O}(X \setminus V_t)$ -convex. \square

Before proving Theorem 3.5, we recall the *localization theorem* and prove the following Lemma 3.13.

Theorem 3.12 (Kusakabe, [15, Theorem 1.4]). *If Y is a complex manifold which is a union of Zariski open Oka domains, then Y is an Oka manifold.*

Lemma 3.13 (cf. [7, Theorem 5.1]). *Let X be a compact complex homogeneous manifold and G be a complex Lie group acting transitively on X . Also, let $\Lambda \subset X$ be a hypersurface. Given an open neighborhood $U_e \subset G$ of the identity element $e := id \in G$, there exist a finite number of elements $e = g_0, g_1, \dots, g_m \in G$ s.t.*

$$\bigcap_{i=0}^m \Lambda_i = \emptyset, \quad \Lambda_i := g_i(\Lambda) \quad (i = 0, \dots, m).$$

Proof. Since $\Lambda \subset X$ is compact, Λ is covered by each open neighborhood of a finite number of representative points $p_1, \dots, p_m \in \Lambda$ on X . In particular, since $\text{Reg}(\Lambda)$ is dense in Λ , we can consider the representative points as non-singular points of Λ . Since G acts transitively on X , for each representative points p , the following holomorphic map is surjective and submersion:

$$\Phi_p : G \rightarrow G/G_p \rightarrow X, \quad g \mapsto [g] \mapsto g \cdot p$$

Let the local expression of Λ at $p \in X$ be $\Lambda = \{f = 0\}$ where $f \in \mathcal{O}(X)$. Then, we consider the holomorphic map on U_e ,

$$f \circ \Phi_p : U_e \rightarrow \mathbb{C}.$$

Note that $f \circ \Phi_p(e) = 0$ and since p is non-singular point of Λ , $d(f \circ \Phi_p)_e \neq 0$. Hence, $f \circ \Phi_p$ is not constantly 0 on U_e . i.e. There exists an element $g_p \in G$ sufficiently close to $e \in G$ s.t. $f \circ \Phi_p(g_p) \neq 0$, that is, $p \notin g_p^{-1}(\Lambda)$. In particular, All points on a sufficiently small open neighborhood of $p \in X$ are not included in $g_p^{-1}(\Lambda)$. For each representative point p_i , we can take such a transformation $g_i := g_{p_i}^{-1}$ and these are what we want. \square

Now, we provide the proof of Theorem 3.5.

Proof of Theorem 3.5. By taking a sufficiently large positive integer $k \gg 0$, $L^{\otimes k}$ becomes very ample, and by considering X as $X \subset \mathbb{P}^N$ by the rational map $\Phi := \Phi_{L^{\otimes k}} : X \rightarrow \mathbb{P}^N$ associated with $|L^{\otimes k}|$, $kV \in |L^{\otimes k}|$ can be considered as the restriction of some hyperplane $\Lambda \subset \mathbb{P}^N$ to be on X : $kV = X \cap \Lambda$. Since \mathbb{P}^N has the complex homogeneous action by the projective transformation $G := \mathbb{P}GL_{n+1}(\mathbb{C})$, and by Lemma 3.13, there exist a finite number of transformations $e = g_0, g_1, \dots, g_m \in G$ that are sufficiently close to $e := id \in G$ and satisfy $\bigcap_{i=0}^m \Lambda_i = \emptyset$, $\Lambda_i := g_i(\Lambda)$ ($i = 0, \dots, m$). In particular, by taking these transformations $e = g_0, g_1, \dots, g_m \in G$ sufficiently close to e , there exists a path $\{g_{i,t}\}_{t \in [0,1]} \subset G$ ($g_{i,0} = g_i, g_{i,1} = e$) that connects each transformation g_i and e , and since Λ satisfies the condition $K \cap \Lambda = K \cap V = \emptyset$, setting $\Lambda_{i,t} := g_{i,t}(\Lambda)$, we get $K \cap \Lambda_{i,t} = \emptyset$ ($t \in [0, 1]$). Note that the transformation $\Lambda_{i,t} = g_{i,t}(\Lambda) \subset \mathbb{P}^N$ of the hypersurface $\Lambda \subset \mathbb{P}^N$ by the projective transformation $g_{i,t} \in \mathbb{P}GL_{n+1}(\mathbb{C})$ is again a hyperplane. The above and the assumptions can be summarized as follows:

- $\{X \cap \Lambda_{i,t}\}_{t \in [0,1]} \subset |L^{\otimes k}|$: path,
- $K \cap (X \cap \Lambda_{i,t}) = \emptyset$, ($t \in [0, 1]$),
- K is compact $\mathcal{O}(X \setminus X \cap \Lambda_{i,1}) (= \mathcal{O}(X \setminus kV))$ -convex.

Therefore, by Theorem 3.3, K is compact $\mathcal{O}(X \setminus X \cap \Lambda_{i,t})$ -convex $\forall t \in [0, 1]$. In particular, if we consider the case of $t = 0$, K is compact $\mathcal{O}(X \setminus X \cap \Lambda_i)$ -convex, ($i = 0, \dots, m$). Since

$$X \setminus X \cap \Lambda_i \simeq X \setminus X \cap \Lambda = X \setminus V,$$

$X \setminus X \cap \Lambda_i$ is a Stein manifold with the density property, and hence, by Theorem 2.14, $(X \setminus X \cap \Lambda_i) \setminus K = (X \setminus K) \setminus (X \cap \Lambda_i)$ is a Zariski open Oka domain in $X \setminus K$. Hence, by the localization theorem (Theorem 3.12),

$$X \setminus K = \bigcup_{i=0}^m ((X \setminus K) \setminus (X \cap \Lambda_i))$$

is Oka. □

As a Corollary of Theorem 3.5, the following holds:

Corollary 3.14. *Suppose that $\Lambda \in \mathcal{V}_{k,l}(\mathbb{P}^n \times \mathbb{P}^m)$ ($k, l > 0$) is given, whose complement $\Omega := \mathbb{P}^n \times \mathbb{P}^m \setminus \Lambda$ has the density property. Then, for any compact $\mathcal{O}(\Omega)$ -convex subset, $\mathbb{P}^n \times \mathbb{P}^m \setminus K$ is Oka.*

Proof. Let $Ver^k : \mathbb{P}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{P}^{\binom{n+k}{k}-1}$ be the Veronese map of degree k , and $Ver^k \times Ver^l : \mathbb{P}^n \times \mathbb{P}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{P}^{\binom{n+k}{k}-1} \times \mathbb{P}^{\binom{m+l}{l}-1}$ be the mapping that applies the Veronese map to each component of the product. Also, let $S = S_{n,m} : \mathbb{P}^n \times \mathbb{P}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{P}^{(n+1)(m+1)-1}$ be the Segre embedding. Finally, let Φ be the embedding by these composite mappings

$$\Phi := S \circ (Ver^k \times Ver^l) : \mathbb{P}^n \times \mathbb{P}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{P}^{\binom{n+k}{k}-1} \times \mathbb{P}^{\binom{m+l}{l}-1} \rightarrow \mathbb{P}^N.$$

Let $\mathbb{P}^n \times \mathbb{P}^m$ be the pull-back of the hyperplane bundle $[H]$ by Φ , then L is a (very) ample bundle over $\mathbb{P}^n \times \mathbb{P}^m$, and since any $\Lambda \in \mathcal{V}_{k,l}(\mathbb{P}^n \times \mathbb{P}^m)$ satisfies $\Lambda \in |L|$, we can apply Theorem 3.5 and then, the statement is proven. □

In order to present another Corollary derived from Theorem 3.5, we will recall some terms.

Definition 3.15 ([8, Definition 1.7]). Let X be a projective manifold and E be a positive line bundle over X . Such a pair (X, E) is called a *polarised manifold*.

- (a) polarised manifold (X, E) satisfies the *polarised density property* if, for any $x \in X$, there exists some divisor $D \in |E|$ s.t. its complement $X \setminus D$ is a Stein neighborhood of x with the density property.
- (b) X satisfies the *polarised density property* if, for any positive line bundle E , the polarised manifold (X, E) satisfies the *polarised density property*.

By Forstnerič and Kusakabe, it is known that the following theorem holds:

Theorem 3.16 (Forstnerič-Kusakabe, [8, Theorem 4.10]). *Every rationally homogeneous manifold satisfies the polarised density property.*

By Theorem 3.5 and Theorem 3.16, the following statement immediately follows:

Corollary 3.17. *For any point $y \in Y$ in a rationally homogeneous manifold Y of dimension at least two, if we take a sufficiently small closed ball B centered at y , then, $Y \setminus B$ is Oka.*

Proof. $\forall y \in Y$, by Theorem 3.16, there exists some positive divisor V on Y s.t. $Y \setminus V$ is a Stein neighborhood of x with the density property. Hence, if we take a closed ball B centered at y which enjoys $B \subset Y \setminus V$, by Theorem 3.5, $Y \setminus B$ is Oka. \square

4 Rationally connected Oka-1 surface without compactification

In this section, we will show that the *complex surface without compactification* constructed in Honda-Nakata [12] has a certain kind of Oka property. When we say that *a complex surface doesn't admit a compactification*, we mean that there is no compact complex surface that includes the complex surface as an open subset.

In the Honda-Nakata's paper [12], such a complex surface is constructed from a domain in $\mathbb{P}^1 \times \mathbb{P}^1$ which is a complement of some compact holomorphically convex subset. However, for the purpose of proof, we construct the complex surface in a slightly different way. Before discussing the specific construction, we will recall the *Oka-1 property*, which is a weaker property than the Oka property.

Definition 4.1 (cf. [1, Definition 1.1]). A complex manifold Y is an *Oka-1 manifold* if maps from Open Riemann surface to Y satisfies the assertion in the Forstnerič's Oka principle (see Theorem 2.4).

From the way of the definition, $\text{Oka} \Rightarrow \text{Oka-1}$. The converse doesn't hold (cf. [18, Theorem 4.5] and [1, Corollary 2.9]).

In order to mention Theorem 4.3 which plays an important role in this section, we recall the *Hausdorff measure*, at first.

Definition 4.2 (Federer [4]). For a subset $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, we arbitrarily take $\delta > 0$ and a countable subset $S_j \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ covering A s.t. $\text{diam}(S_j) := \sup\{|x - y| ; x, y \in S_j\} < \delta$, then we define the m -dimensional Hausdorff measure $\mathcal{H}^m(A)$ of A as follows:

$$\mathcal{H}^m(A) = \lim_{\delta \rightarrow 0} \inf_{A \subset \bigcup_{S_j} S_j} \sum_{\text{diam}(S_j) \leq \delta} \alpha_m \left(\frac{\text{diam}(S_j)}{2} \right)^m$$

Here α_m is the volume $\alpha_m = \mathcal{L}^m(\mathbb{B}^m)$ of the m -dimensional unit ball \mathbb{B}^m with respect to the Lebesgue measure \mathcal{L}^m .

Theorem 4.3 (cf. Alarcón-Forstnerič [1, Theorem 2.2]). *Let Y be a complex manifold of dimension n . Suppose there exists a closed subset $E \subset Y$ s.t. $\mathcal{H}^{2n-1}(E) = 0$ and Y is strongly dominable at every point of $Y \setminus E$. Then, Y is Oka-1.*

Remark 4.4. Let Y be a complex manifold of dimension n .

- (i) Y is called *densely dominable*, if Y satisfies the assumption in Theorem 4.3.
- (ii) Clearly, for any analytic subset $V \subset Y$, $\mathcal{H}^{2n-1}(V) = 0$.

From Theorem 4.3 and Remark 4.4, the following statement follows immediately:

Corollary 4.5 ([1, Corollary 2.5]). *Let Y be a complex manifold which contains a dominable Zariski open subset. Then, Y is Oka-1.*

From now, we will explain the method of constructing the complex surface without compactification which is Oka-1.

First, take five different fibers l_1, l_2, l_3, l_4 and D , and two different sections s_0 and s_1 on $\mathbb{P}^1 \times \mathbb{P}^1$. Also, for each of D and s_0 , take an open neighborhood which is biholomorphic with $\Delta \times \mathbb{P}^1$, and let $T_1 \subset \mathbb{P}^1 \times \mathbb{P}^1$ be their union. Here, Δ is a complex open disk on the affine coordinate \mathbb{C} in \mathbb{P}^1 . Furthermore, taken appropriately, the open neighborhood centered on s_0 doesn't intersect with s_1 , and the open neighborhood centered on D doesn't intersect with l_1, l_2, l_3 and l_4 (Figure 1).

Let p_1, p_2, p_3 and p_4 the intersection points of l_1 with s_0 , l_2 with s_0 , l_3 with s_1 and l_4 with s_1 respectively, and let $\mu_1 : \mathbb{P}^1 \times \mathbb{P}^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{P}^1 \times \mathbb{P}^1$ be the blow-up of these four points in $\mathbb{P}^1 \times \mathbb{P}^1$. We note that the proper transforms of l_1, l_2, l_3 and l_4 is expressed by the same symbols respectively. Let E_1, E_2, E_3 and E_4 be the exceptional curves over p_1, p_2, p_3 and p_4 respectively.

Then, Let $\mu_2 : \mathbb{P}^1 \times \mathbb{P}^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{P}^1 \times \mathbb{P}^1$ be the blow-down of four (-1) -curves l_1, l_2, l_3 and l_4 in $\mathbb{P}^1 \times \mathbb{P}^1$. For each D_1 and s_1 in $\mu_2(\mathbb{P}^1 \times \mathbb{P}^1) = \mathbb{P}^1 \times \mathbb{P}^1$, we take an open neighborhood which is biholomorphic with $\Delta \times \mathbb{P}^1$ respectively, and let $T_2 \subset \mathbb{P}^1 \times \mathbb{P}^1$ be their union. We set $\tilde{U} := \mu_1^{-1}(T_1) \cup \mu_2^{-1}(T_2)$.

Second, we take a sufficiently small open neighborhood $W_1 \subset T_1$ of the point $p_1 \in T_1$, and similarly take a sufficiently small open neighborhood $W_2 \subset T_2$ of the point which is the intersection of E_1 and s_1 . Then, let \hat{U} be the new complex manifold obtained by replacing the subset $\mu_1^{-1}(W_1) \cup \mu_2^{-1}(W_2)$ in \tilde{U} with the disjoint union $\mu_1^{-1}(W_1) \sqcup \mu_2^{-1}(W_2)$. Let $\nu : \hat{U} \rightarrow \tilde{U}$ be the mapping defined to consider the disjoint union $\mu_1^{-1}(W_1) \sqcup \mu_2^{-1}(W_2)$ as the previous set $\mu_1^{-1}(W_1) \cup \mu_2^{-1}(W_2)$:

$$\nu(\mu_1^{-1}(W_1) \sqcup \mu_2^{-1}(W_2)) = \mu_1^{-1}(W_1) \cup \mu_2^{-1}(W_2).$$

This map is holomorphic.

Figure 1. $\tilde{U} = \mu_1^{-1}(T_1) \cup \mu_2^{-1}(T_2)$

Finally, let $\sigma_1 : \hat{U} \rightarrow \hat{U}'$ be the blow-down of l_1 and E_1 in \hat{U} , and $\sigma_2 : \hat{U}' \rightarrow \check{U}$ be the blow-down of s_0 and s_1 in \hat{U}' .

Theorem 4.6 (cf. Honda-Nakata [12, Theorem 4.6]). *\check{U} doesn't admit a compactification as a complex surface.*

Lemma 4.7 (Noether's lemma). *Any compact complex manifold containing a smooth rational curve whose self-intersection number is positive is rational surface.*

Proof of Theorem 4.6. On \check{U} , there exists the rational curve D whose self-intersection number is two. If there were compact complex surface S containing \check{U} , by the Noether's lemma, S would be a rational surface. On the other hand, by the Riemann-Roch theorem on a complex surface, any smooth rational curve whose self-intersection number is two should satisfy $\dim|C| = 3$. However, D satisfies $\dim|D| = 1$ ([12, Proposition 4.4]). This is contradictory. \square

Remark 4.8. Since \check{U} doesn't admit a compactification, its blow-ups \hat{U} and \hat{U}' also.

Figure 2. Complex surface \check{U} without compactification.

Proposition 4.9. $T_1 \setminus s_0$ is Oka.

Proof. This is proven by using the method in Theorem 3.5. We set $\Lambda := s_0 \cup D$, and then $\mathbb{P}^1 \times \mathbb{P}^1 \setminus \Lambda \simeq \mathbb{C}^2$. Also, we set $K := \mathbb{P}^1 \times \mathbb{P}^1 \setminus T_1$, and then K is a compact holomorphically convex subset in the affine coordinate \mathbb{C}^2 . By Corollary 2.15,

$$T_1 \setminus \Lambda = (\mathbb{P}^1 \times \mathbb{P}^1 \setminus K) \setminus \Lambda = (\mathbb{P}^1 \times \mathbb{P}^1 \setminus \Lambda) \setminus K \simeq \mathbb{C}^2 \setminus K$$

is Oka. Let D' be a fiber obtained by slightly translating D parallel to along s_0 , and we set $\Lambda' := s_0 \cup D'$. Then $T_1 \setminus \Lambda'$ is also Oka. By the localization theorem, the following domain is Oka:

$$T_1 \setminus s_0 = (T_1 \setminus \Lambda) \cup (T_1 \setminus \Lambda').$$

□

Remark 4.10. We can take hypersurfaces Λ_1 and Λ_2 instead of the $\Lambda_0 := \Lambda$ in Proposition 4.9, which are obtained by slightly translating s_0 and D , and then satisfy $\bigcap_{i=0}^2 \Lambda_i = \emptyset$. Thus, by the localization theorem, $T_1 = \bigcup_{i=0}^2 (T_1 \setminus \Lambda_i)$ itself is also Oka. Similarly, $T_2 \setminus s_1$ and T_2 are Oka.

Definition 4.11. A complex manifold Y is *rationally connected*, if, for any two points $x, y \in Y$, there exist a finite number of holomorphic maps $f_j : \mathbb{P}^1 \rightarrow Y$, ($j = 1, \dots, m$) s.t. $x \in f_1(\mathbb{P}^1)$, $y \in f_m(\mathbb{P}^1)$, $f_j(\mathbb{P}^1) \cap f_{j+1}(\mathbb{P}^1) \neq \emptyset$, ($j = 1, \dots, m-1$).

Remark 4.12. rationally connected $\Rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ -connected.

Proposition 4.13. \hat{U} is rationally connected.

Proof. T_1 is rationally connected due to fibers and sections within it. In particular, $T_1 \setminus \{p_1, p_2\} \simeq \mu_1^{-1}(T_1) \setminus (E_1 \cup E_2)$ and any two points outside s_0 on $T_1 \setminus \{p_1, p_2\}$ are connected by a finite chain of \mathbb{P}^1 (Figure 3). Also, any point p on $E_1 \cup E_2 \cup s_0$ in $\mu_1^{-1}(T_1)$ can be connected to any point q outside $E_1 \cup E_2 \cup s_0$ by rational curves E_1, E_2, s_0 and D (Figure 4). i.e. any point on $E_1 \cup E_2 \cup s_0$ in $\mu_1^{-1}(T_1)$ can be connected to any point outside $E_1 \cup E_2 \cup s_0$ by a finite chain of rational curves. From the above observation, $\mu_1^{-1}(T_1)$ is rationally connected. Similarly, $\mu_2^{-1}(T_2)$ is also rationally connected. Since $\mu_1^{-1}(T_1)$ and $\mu_2^{-1}(T_2)$ share the common domain, $\tilde{U} = \mu_1^{-1}(T_1) \cup \mu_2^{-1}(T_2)$ is also rationally connected. In particular, since the two domains $\mu_1^{-1}(T_1)$ and $\mu_2^{-1}(T_2)$ in \tilde{U} are respectively rationally connected, \tilde{U} is rationally connected without considering rational curves that straddles the open neighborhood centered on E_1 and the open neighborhood centered on l_1 . Therefore, \hat{U} , which is obtained by separating the open neighborhood centered on E_1 (let $T(E_1)$ be this domain) and the open neighborhood centered on l_1 (let $T(l_1)$ be this domain), is also rationally connected (Figure 5). □

Remark 4.14. By Proposition 4.13 and the following Lemma 4.15, \hat{U}' and \check{U} are also rationally connected respectively.

Lemma 4.15. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a surjective holomorphic map from X to Y and X be rationally connected. Then, the image Y by f is rationally connected.

Proof. For any two points $a, b \in Y$, from surjectivity of f , there exist two points $p, q \in X$ s.t. $f(p) = a$, $f(q) = b$. By the assumption, X is rationally connected, so there are a finite number of holomorphic maps $f_j : \mathbb{P}^1 \rightarrow X$, ($j = 1, \dots, m$) s.t.

$$p \in f_1(\mathbb{P}^1), q \in f_m(\mathbb{P}^1), f_j(\mathbb{P}^1) \cap f_{j+1}(\mathbb{P}^1) \neq \emptyset, (j = 1, \dots, m-1).$$

By setting $g_j := f \circ f_j$ ($j = 1, \dots, m-1$), then $g_j \in \mathcal{O}(\mathbb{P}^1, Y)$, ($j = 1, \dots, m-1$) and

$$a \in g_1(\mathbb{P}^1), b \in g_m(\mathbb{P}^1), g_j(\mathbb{P}^1) \cap g_{j+1}(\mathbb{P}^1) \neq \emptyset, (j = 1, \dots, m-1).$$

Therefore, Y is rationally connected. □

Figure 3. Any two points outside s_0 in $T_1 \setminus \{p_1, p_2\} \simeq \mu_1^{-1}(T_1) \setminus (E_1 \cup E_2)$ are connected by fibers and sections (In this figure, q_1 and q_2 are connected by one fiber and two sections).

Figure 4. Any point on $E_1 \cup E_2 \cup s_0$ is connected to any point outside $E_1 \cup E_2 \cup s_0$ by $E_1 \cup E_2 \cup s_0$ itself and D (In this figure, q_1 on E_1 is connected to q_4 outside $E_1 \cup E_2 \cup s_0$ via points q_2 and q_3).

Figure 5. \hat{U} is rationally connected via the open neighborhood centered on D (In this figure, q_1 on $\mu_1^{-1}(T_1)$ and q_4 on $\mu_2^{-1}(T_2)$ are connected via points q_2 and q_3).

Proposition 4.16. \hat{U}' is densely dominable, and hence Oka-1.

Proof. By Proposition 4.9,

$$(4.1) \quad T_1 \setminus s_0 \simeq \mu_1^{-1}(T_1) \setminus (s_0 \cup E_1 \cup E_2) : \text{Oka} (\implies \text{strongly dominable}),$$

$$(4.2) \quad T_2 \setminus s_1 \simeq \mu_2^{-1}(T_2) \setminus (s_1 \cup l_1 \cup l_2) : \text{Oka} (\implies \text{strongly dominable}).$$

Since (4.1) and (4.2) are strongly dominable respectively, the following domain obtained by separating $\mu_1^{-1}(T_1) \setminus (s_0 \cup E_1 \cup E_2)$ and $\mu_2^{-1}(T_2) \setminus (s_1 \cup l_1 \cup l_2)$ at the common part of $T(E_1)$ and $T(l_1)$ is also strongly dominable (see Figure 2):

$$(4.3) \quad \hat{U} \setminus ((s_0 \setminus \Delta_0) \cup (s_1 \setminus \Delta_1) \cup E_1 \cup E_2 \cup l_1 \cup l_2).$$

Here, let Δ_0 be the one-dimensional complex open disk on s_0 that is cut by the open neighborhood centered on D , and let Δ_1 be the one-dimensional complex open disk on s_1 that is cut by the open neighborhood centered on D (Figure 2). Then, the following domain that is biholomorphic with (4.3) by the blow-down σ_1 is strongly dominable:

$$(4.4) \quad \hat{U}' \setminus ((s_0 \setminus \Delta_0) \cup (s_1 \setminus \Delta_1) \cup E_2 \cup l_2).$$

Since $\mathcal{H}^3((s_0 \setminus \Delta_0) \cup (s_1 \setminus \Delta_1) \cup E_2 \cup l_2) = 0$, \hat{U}' is densely dominable, and hence, by Theorem 4.3, \hat{U}' is Oka-1. \square

Remark 4.17. By the definition, for any two strongly dominable domains $U_1, U_2 \subset Y$ in a complex manifold Y , the union $U_1 \cup U_2 \subset Y$ is also strongly dominable.

Remark 4.18. Since (4.3) is strongly dominable, \hat{U} is densely dominable, and hence Oka-1.

Therefore, we have shown the following another main result in this paper:

Theorem 4.19. \widehat{U}' is a rationally connected densely dominable Oka-1 surface without compactification.

Furthermore, From the argument in Forstnerič-Lárusson [3, Theorem 11], if blowing up Y in the discrete subset $E \subset X$ in a n -dimensional complex manifold X enjoys the basic Oka property with approximation with respect to holomorphic maps from Stein manifolds with dimension less than n , then X also enjoys the same property. Therefore, for the minitwistor space \widehat{U} , the following holds:

Theorem 4.20. \check{U} is a rationally connected surface without compactification, and enjoys the basic Oka-1 property with approximation.

Finally, the following problem can be considered to ask whether the complex surface constructed in this way without compactification has stronger holomorphic flexibility.

Problem 4.21. Is \check{U} Oka-1 or even Oka?

Problem 4.22. Is \widehat{U} strongly dominable, Oka or even elliptic?

Problem 4.21 asks whether

$$\widehat{U}' \setminus (s_0 \cup s_1 \cup E_2 \cup l_2)$$

obtained by removing Δ_0 and Δ_1 from (4.4) is Oka-1. In particular, the problem is whether we can take a general holomorphic map $X \rightarrow \widehat{U}'$ from an open Riemann surface in such a way as to avoid Δ_0 and Δ_1 . Such a problem has been solved in a special case by Forstnerič (cf. [1, Corollary 2.9]).

One of the obstacles when considering Problem 4.22 is the question “Does *Oka* be preserved by blow-ups?” In the case of algebraic manifolds, there are some results that positively solve this question (cf. Kusakabe, [13]). In order to avoid such a difficulty in our discussion, we decided to focus on dominability in the domain excluding exceptional curves. Note that a compactification of the complex surface is lost after the separating operation, and then such a structural change might destroy holomorphic flexibility of the complex surface.

Regarding ellipticity, there is the following Conjecture.

Conjecture 4.23 (The Cerveau conjecture in Elliptic Geometry). There is no elliptic domain with smooth boundaries in \mathbb{P}^n .

From this Conjecture, it is very doubtful that \widehat{U} is elliptic.

As the more general question of Problem 4.21, the following can be considered.

Question 4.24. Is Any (mini)twistor space Oka?

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